

ELIZABETHAN POETRY, DRAMA AND FICTION

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Abstract: English literature has been developed in some period. Each period has its own characteristics which portrayed the condition of the age. The period of English literature is started from Old English until Modern English. English literature becomes glorious when Queen Elizabeth I ruled England. This age is known as Elizabethan period.

Key words: Elizabethan literature, elizabethan poetry/drama, renaissance, the golden age of english literature.

In Elizabethan period there are many literary works such as poetry, drama which are produced by famous artists. The literary works produced in Elizabethan period is famous and the existence of the literary works can be seen nowadays. Furthermore, some literary works, such as drama, are reproduced into movie. Therefore, this period is also known as the golden age of English Literature. Human life experiences can be portrayed in any form of literary works such as poetry, drama, novel, etc. Those literary works develop as well as the development of civilization because literary works are the creation of human being and human being always develops every time.

This condition can be seen in English Literature. English literature develops in some period. Every period has its own characteristics. Elizabethan period is regarded as the greatest development of English literature. The age of Elizabeth is characterized by abundance of production in branch of literature especially poetry and drama. The literary works of Elizabethan period are very famous and also can be found until now. Therefore, Elizabethan period is known as the golden age of English literature. Elizabethan period started in 1550 until 1600. This period is called Elizabethan period because in that time England was ruled by the great Queen Elizabeth I. Queen Elizabeth I came to the throne in 1558 and ended in 1603. In the previous period, English literature has many rules which must be followed by the artists, so they cannot express their feeling freely because of the rules. In Elizabethan period, these rules have been left out. Therefore, the artists can express their feeling freely without being afraid to break the rules. As the result, there are so many literary works produced in this period. The artists seem to revive after binding by the rules.

This period is also known as Renaissance period. The famous poet in this period is Edmund Spenser who was born in London in 1533. He finished his

study in Cambridge in 1576. In 1594, he married Elizabeth Boyle and had four children. He died in 1599 at the age of 47. Edmund Spenser is known as the greatest poet of the age. His famous poem is the Faery Queen. Spenser starts to write a poem which consists of twelve parts which every part tells about the adventure of a knight. Spenser can only finish six parts from twelve parts that he planned before.

From all literary works, drama is regarded as the greatest literary work in Elizabethan period. Drama not only teaches the morality, but also portrays the life of people. Every drama tells a problem. Drama can be tragedy which is full of sadness or can be comedy which is full of happiness. The structure of a drama usually begins with exposition, complication or climax, and denouement. Exposition is a stage for introducing a problem. Complication or climax is a stage where the problem becomes complicated. Finally, denouement is problem solving. These stages are usually arranged in some acts and scenes (Samekto, 1974:19).

Edmund Spenser (c. 1552–99) was one of the most important poets of this period, author of *The Faerie Queene* (1590 and 1596), an epic poem and fantastical allegory celebrating the Tudor dynasty and Elizabeth I. Another major figure, Sir Philip Sidney (1554–86), was an English poet, courtier and soldier, and is remembered as one of the most prominent figures of the Elizabethan Age. His works include *Astrophel and Stella*, *An Apology for Poetry*, and *The Countess of Pembroke's Arcadia*. Poems intended to be set to music as songs, such as by Thomas Campion (1567–1620), became popular as printed literature was disseminated more widely in households. See English Madrigal School.

Human life experiences can be portrayed in any form of literary works such as poetry, drama, novel, etc. Those literary works develop as well as the development of civilization because literary works are the creation of human being and human being always develops every time. This condition can be seen in English Literature. From all period, Elizabethan period is regarded as the greatest development of English literature because it is characterized by abundance of production in branch of literature especially poetry and drama. The literary works of Elizabethan period are very famous and also can be found until now. In this period, there is a greatest dramatist in the world named William Shakespeare which has written some famous drama, namely *Julius Caesar*, *The Merchant of Venice*, *Romeo and Juliet*, *Hamlet*. Therefore, Elizabethan period is known as the golden age of English literature.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Abrams, M.H., et al. 1962. The Norton Anthology of English Literature. New York: Norton.
2. Alexander, Michael. 2000. A History of English Literature. New York: Palgrave.
3. Alexander, Peter. 1951. William Shakespeare, The Complete Works. London: Collins.
4. Baugh, Albert C. 1957. A History of the English Literature. New York: Appleton.
5. Departemen Pendidikan Nasional. 2005. Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia. Jakarta: Balai Pustaka.